

TOWARD AN ACCURATE FAILURE CRITERION OF ANISOTROPIC MATERIALS, A NEW FLEXURE TEST CONSIDERING THE COUPLING EFFECT

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SUMMARY: This work aims to propose a new simple test procedure that aims to give an accurate evaluation of the strength of an off-axis unidirectional lamina. After obtaining positive results from a 3D finite element analysis investigating the stress state due to the coupling effect in off-axis unidirectional specimens under bending loads, we could prove the utility of designing and using a test machine that allows specimens to twist as well as flex while deforming under these loads. Furthermore, this analysis has proven that the specimen bending stress at failure could be computed with a good approximation by using the simple beam theory. Consequently, the In-plane stress state in the specimen could be defined. And the failure envelope in σ_{12} - σ_{22} domain, and a 3D representation, in the space defined by the axes σ_{11} , σ_{12} and σ_{22} were plotted. This failure envelope has good potential to be used as a failure criterion to evaluate the lamina cracking resistance.

KEYWORDS: Off-axis Specimen, Flexure Test, Coupling Effect, Finite Element stress Analysis, Ply Strength, Failure Criterion.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that an optimum design of a laminate structure demands the knowledge of the laminate strength. However, as the lamina is the building block of a laminate, so it was obvious that the study of a laminate must start by studying the strength of one lamina. In the composite research works, we can see that many works were conducted to investigate this point and to try to define an accurate failure criterion for a lamina under a multi-axial stress state. The major obstacle that researchers faced was from one side the costly biaxial tests and the complex stress status due to the material anisotropy.

First, and in order to enlighten the coupling effect caused by the material anisotropy, we will summarize the in-plane stress-strain relations of an angle lamina.

Fig. 1 shows an angle lamina to which two coordinate systems were defined. The axes in the 1-2 coordinate system, called the local or material axes, are defined so that the direction 1 is parallel to the fibers (longitudinal direction L), and the direction 2 is perpendicular to them (transverse direction T). The axes in the x-y coordinate system are called the global axes or off-axes. The angle between the two axes is denoted by an angle α .

Fig. 1: Local and global axes of an angle lamina

In the local axes, the lamina can be seen as effective, homogenous, transversely isotropic material, so stress-strain relations can be written as:

$$[\varepsilon]_{1,2,3} = [S][\sigma]_{1,2,3}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

By inverting the previous equations, we can write:

$$[\sigma]_{1,2,3} = [Q][\varepsilon]_{1,2,3}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where [Q] is the reduced stiffness matrix.

However, the global and local stresses in an angle lamina are related to each other by the angle of the lamina, θ .

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [T]^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where [T] is called the transformation matrix and is defined as:

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & 2sc \\ s^2 & c^2 & -2sc \\ -sc & sc & c^2 - s^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Where $c = \cos(\alpha)$ and $s = \sin(\alpha)$.

Using the stress-strain Eqn 2 written in the local axes, Eqn 3 can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [T]^{-1}[Q] \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, global and local strains are also related through [T]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} / 2 \end{bmatrix} = [T] \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} / 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

If we use the Reuter Matrix [R], defined as:

$$[R] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

So we can write:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = [R][T][R]^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Then substituting of Eqn 7 in Eqn 5 gives:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [T]^{-1}[Q][R][T][R]^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Hence, the transformed reduced stiffness matrix is defined by:

$$[\overline{Q}] = [T]^{-1}[Q][R][T][R]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{Q}_{11} & \overline{Q}_{12} & \overline{Q}_{16} \\ \overline{Q}_{12} & \overline{Q}_{22} & \overline{Q}_{26} \\ \overline{Q}_{16} & \overline{Q}_{26} & \overline{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

It is to be noted that the six elements in this matrix are nonzero, they are just functions of the four stiffness elements in the matrix [Q] and the lamina's angle α .

By inverting this matrix we can define the transformed reduced compliance matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{S}_{11} & \overline{S}_{12} & \overline{S}_{16} \\ \overline{S}_{12} & \overline{S}_{22} & \overline{S}_{26} \\ \overline{S}_{16} & \overline{S}_{26} & \overline{S}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

From Eqn 1 and Eqn 3, which define the stress-strain relations for a unidirectional lamina loaded in the material axes directions, there is no coupling between the normal and shearing

terms of strains and stresses. However, for an angle lamina, from Eqn 10 and Eqn 11 we can see that there is coupling between the normal and shearing terms of strains and stresses.

This phenomena, called the coupling effect, is the cause of the inaccuracies in using a classical tensile test machine to evaluate the off-axis specimen's strength. In this case, a nonuniform stress state is produced by the end constrains. This is why it was necessary to think about either a better gripping system that eliminates this stress concentration or another test procedure that leads to more accuracy in the evaluation of lamina strength Ref. 1.

In this work, we propose the use of the flexure test for the study of the stress state of an off-axis unidirectional laminate. In this bending test, the coupling effect will be again responsible of a similar problem to what we have seen in the tensile test. That is, the off-axis unidirectional specimen will develop twist as well as flexure as it deforms under the three-point bending loads. This twist will introduce an undesirable stress concentration at the specimen grips, which will be the cause of a nonuniform stress state.

To solve this problem we propose a specimen holder that has rotating supports. To evaluate this idea, a 3-D finite element stress analysis has been conducted on an off-axis specimen under bending load.

Fig. 2.a shows the computational result obtained by the finite element method of the stress state in an off-axis specimen constrained against twisting at its ends and loaded in bending.

Similarly, Fig. 2.b shows the same analysis but without constraining the twisting at the ends.

Fig. 2.a: Bending with constrained twisting

Fig. 2.b: Bending with non-constrained twisting

Based on the comparison of these two analyses, we see the importance of improving the supporting condition by allowing the specimen to twist by means of rotating supports. Further improvement could be obtained by allowing each of these supports to rotate also around the contact line with the specimen. See Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Schematic representation of the supports

SPECIMEN'S CONFIGURATION AND LOADING CONDITION

In this work, the specimens are unidirectional off-axis specimens that were taken out of the same $[0_{24}]$ T800/3631 laminate plate. The 24 plies of this plate are made up of continuous; unidirectional fibers embedded in a matrix. This plate was cut to obtain unidirectional off-axis specimens with different fiber that have fibers at an angle to the sides of the specimen.

The specimens were identical in their dimensions. Each specimen is of length " L "= 60 mm, width " b "= 10 mm and thickness " h "= 3 mm. While the fiber angle is different from one specimen to another. Accordingly we have the specimens with fiber angles of 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° . This difference in the fiber angles will enable us to obtain a range of stress states. Fig. 5 shows the configuration of a specimen together with the loading condition in which the span " l "= 46.5 mm.

Fig. 4: The configuration of the plate cutting condition

Fig. 5: Test specimen and Loading

The test specimens were loaded to failure by using a hydraulically actuated testing machine. As previously mentioned, the specimen holder was designed so that while deforming under the bending load, the specimen is allowed to twist as well as to flex. Fig. 6 shows the specimen holder we used in our tests.

Fig. 6: Photos of the specimen holder

ANALYSIS

By conducting the 3-D finite element stress analysis using the SACOM3D, a software developed in our laboratory, we aimed to analyze the stress state of a unidirectional off-axis specimen under bending load. Furthermore, we wanted to evaluate the possibility of using the Simple Beam Theory to evaluate the failure stress in this specimen.

As the failure of the unidirectional off-axis specimen is expected to initiate at the bottom surface of the specimen and at its midspan, so we have chosen to make a 3-D finite element model of the consisting of 20 noded isoparametric elements with mesh refinement at the midspan as well as at the load reaction sites.

The elastic properties used to represent this specimen were defined as follows:

$E_{11}= 183.384$ GPa, $E_{22}= E_{33}= 9.28$ GPa

$G_{12}= G_{13}= 4.29$ GPa, $G_{23}= 3.99$ GPa

$\nu_{12}= 0.255$, $\nu_{13}= 0.162$, $\nu_{23}= 0.013$

The loading was modeled as a uniform load in the Z direction applied on the transversal nodes at the midspan of the upper surface.

The finite element stress analysis was conducted for four types of specimen, those of a fiber angel equals to 15° , 45° , 60° and 75° .

In Fig. 7.a, 7.b, 7.c and 7.d the results of these analyses are plotted to show the stress distributions across the specimen's width and at the midspan. As we want to investigate the possible use of the simple beam theory to define the stress state in the specimen and for easier comparison, these stresses were normalized by σ_{xb} , which is the maximum stress calculated by the simple beam theory. σ_{xb} is calculated by the following equation:

$$\sigma_{xb} = \frac{3Pl}{2bh^2} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 7.a: Analysis result for 15°

Fig. 7.b: Analysis result for 45°

Fig. 7.c: Analysis result for 60°

Fig. 7.d: Analysis result for 75°

From these results we can see that the stresses other than σ_{xx} are comparatively small, while σ_{xx} has almost the same value as σ_{xb} . Thus, we can say that the simple beam theory can describe quantitatively the mechanical behavior of the specimen. In other words, we can use this theory with confidence to quantify the failure of these off-axis specimens.

The axial bending stress σ_{xx} produces a multi-axial stress state on the failure plan, this stress that could be considered equal in value to σ_{xb} , can be further resolved into components along the material principal axes. This resolution gives σ_{22} which is the normal stress transverse to the fiber, and σ_{12} which is the longitudinal shear stress in the fiber direction. The values of σ_{12} and σ_{22} are consequently defined by the following relations:

$$\sigma_{22} = \sigma_{xb} \sin^2 \alpha \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{12} = \sigma_{xb} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \quad (14)$$

TEST AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Bending tests using this bending apparatus were conducted on six types of off-axis specimen. For each type of specimens, characterized by the same fiber angle, the test was done for three specimens. As expected, all specimens failed by cracking from their bottom surface. The cracks were initiated at the specimen midspan and developed in the fiber direction. Fig. 8 shows three of these specimens after failure.

Fig. 8: The 15°, 45°, 60° and 75° Specimens after failure

The results of these tests are classified into three types.

First, the relation between the load and the displacement at the specimen's midspan. Fig. 9 shows the load-displacement curves obtained for the different specimens.

From these curves, we can see that this relation isn't perfectly linear. This non-linearity might be due in part to the occurrence of matrix yielding.

Fig. 9: Bending P- δ curves for different fiber orientations

Second, the relation between the fiber angle and the maximum twist angle (twist angle at failure). Fig. 10 shows that the value of this angle depends on the fiber angle.

Fig. 10: Relation between fiber orientation and twist angle

Finally, the curves showing how σ_{12} rates with and σ_{22} and this for the different fiber angles. As previously mentioned σ_{22} and σ_{12} at failure can be calculated by using the value of the Eqn 13 and Eqn 14. For this σ_{xb} can be calculated using Eqn 12, where P is the maximum load at failure obtained by the test.

In order to plot the values of σ_{22} against σ_{12} for the different cases of fiber orientation we conducted the same test on three samples that have the same fiber orientation. In Fig. 11, a solid circle is the average of the three samples corresponding to the same fiber orientation.

By linking these average points by a curve, we obtain the specimen failure curve in σ_{12} - σ_{22} domain.

Fig. 11: Failure curve in σ_{12} - σ_{22}

It is to be noted that as the above failure curve relates only the values of σ_{22} to σ_{12} , thus it doesn't give a complete information about the specimen's stress status at failure. For this we still need to include the value of σ_{11} .

In fact the experimental results showed that σ_{11} has a considerable influence on the specimen's failure behavior especially in case of small fiber orientation angles. . By including

the values of σ_{11} , the following figure is a 3D representation of what we can call the failure envelope of the specimen.

Fig. 12: A 3D representation of the failure envelop in σ_{11} , σ_{12} , σ_{22} domain

CONCLUSIONS

A simulation made by 3-D finite element stress analysis of an off-axis specimen under a bending load has demonstrated the utility and necessity of allowing such a specimen to twist as well as to flex when it is under bending loads. As a result, we eliminate the effect of the resisting torque at the ends, and we can reach a uniform stress state in the specimen. This simulation has led to the design of the new specimen holder for bending test.

The 3-D finite element stress analysis of different types of unidirectional off-axis specimen under bending loads has also shown that the simple beam theory could be used with confidence to analyze the stress state at the specimen midspan. The use of this theory enabled us to calculate the In-plane stresses, σ_{12} and σ_{22} of the specimen.

A series of tests was carried out on unidirectional off-axis specimens that only differ by their fiber angles. These tests, and by the use of the simple beam theory, led to the evaluation of the In-plane stress state at the specimen midspan. The curves in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 could be seen and considered as a lamina failure criterion.

In future study, this point will be investigated in depth. A possible use of the results of tests, done not only on unidirectional plies but also on laminate, to obtain a failure criterion for ply cracking resistance as well as for typical laminate structures.

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